

Spectrum of Congenital Heart Diseases Seen in the Department of Paediatrics, Federal Medical Centre, Abuja, Nigeria: A 5-Year Retrospective Study

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ABSTRACT

Congenital heart disease (CHD) is the commonest birth defect worldwide, accounting for approximately 8 per 1000 live births. CHD is associated with increased morbidity and mortality, especially in low- and medium-income countries, which usually lack access to early diagnosis and definitive surgical treatment and care. Recent studies have shown an increasing burden of this disease. This study aimed to document the prevalence and pattern of CHD among children at Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Abuja. This was a hospital-based retrospective observational study. The records of all children seen at the Department of Paediatrics, FMC Abuja, who underwent echocardiography between 2020 and 2024 were reviewed. The clinical, demographic, and echocardiogram details were retrieved. Descriptive analysis was conducted with Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), version 26. A total of 391 children were identified to have heart disease, out of which 343 (87.8%) had CHD. Of the 343 patients, 185 (53.9%) were male and 158 (46.1%) females with a male-to-female ratio of 1.1:1. Ventricular septal defect (24.9%) was the commonest acyanotic CHD while Tetralogy of Fallot (34.5%) was the most prevalent cyanotic CHD. The prevalence of CHD in this study gradually increased from 12% in 2020 to 33.2% in 2024. Trisomy 21 (73.2%) was the most frequently identified chromosomal abnormality. Sixteen (4.7%) of the patients died. The spectrum of CHD in our study is similar to previous documentations in the literatures. The mortality rate is still high, largely due to the non-availability of affordable surgical intervention despite early diagnosis.

Keywords: Congenital heart disease, Tetralogy of Fallot, Ventricular septal defect

INTRODUCTION

Congenital heart disease (CHD) is defined as a gross structural abnormality of the heart or intrathoracic great vessels that is actually or potentially of functional significance which is present at birth even if it is discovered later.^{1,2} CHD are the leading cause of birth defects with an incidence of 8/1000 live births and 2-3 out of 1000 new born infants being symptomatic

with heart disease in the first year of life thereby constituting a major global health problem.³⁻⁶ The birth prevalence of CHD varies among studies worldwide and is mostly reported between 8 and 12 per 1000 with approximately 1.35 million new-borns born with CHD every year globally.⁶⁻¹¹ The incidence of CHD in Nigeria has increased over the years from 3.5 per 1000 population that was documented about 3 decades ago to

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14.4 per 1,000 reported few years ago.^{12,13}

CHD varies in severity, occurring from communications between cavities that spontaneously regress to major malformations that might require several procedures, by catheterization or by surgical means.^{14,15} Amongst the acyanotic cardiac lesions, studies have shown that ventricular septal defects (VSD) are the commonest CHD seen while tetralogy of Fallot and transposition of the great arteries are the commonest cyanotic lesions seen depending on the population studied.^{16,17} A significant proportion of children born with CHD may lead a normal, productive life if diagnosed early and appropriate medical/surgical intervention instituted but majority tend to die due to lack of timely access to care.^{18,19} In Nigeria, there has been improvement in early detection of children with congenital heart disease and subsequent referral to centres that offer echocardiography studies for definitive diagnosis. The bane of congenital heart disease in Nigeria is now the availability of operative services due to lack of skilled personnel, equipment and the high cost of this service. Though diagnosis is made on time, some of the children succumb to the complication of the particular heart condition due to delay in accessing definitive intervention. Echocardiographic evaluation remains the gold standard for the diagnosis of structural cardiac disease. There has not been any report on the pattern of CHD in Federal Capital Territory. Therefore, we undertook this retrospective hospital-based study to estimate the frequency and pattern of CHD in children attending one of referral hospital in Federal Capital Territory.

The aim of this study was to document the prevalence and the patterns of CHD seen in Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Abuja, Nigeria. This information will not only contribute to the available data on CHD, but will also help to improve policies regarding the services offered to these children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

A retrospective descriptive study of all children seen in both the in-and out-patient units of the department of

paediatrics, Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Abuja who had an echocardiography carried out on them between January 1, 2020 and December 31, 2024

Study setting

FMC Abuja is a Federal owned tertiary health facility that serves the Federal Capital Territory and receives referral from all over Nigeria including her neighbouring states of Kogi, Niger, Kaduna, Nasarawa and Plateau. The paediatric cardiology unit is manned by two (2) Paediatric Cardiologist with resident doctors who rotate through the unit.

Data collection

The records of all the children seen (both in-and out-patients) in the paediatric cardiology units of FMC Abuja who had echocardiography performed on them were retrieved and reviewed. Diagnosis was analysed based on echocardiographic reports. Those who have no echocardiographic confirmation of their diagnosis were excluded from the final analysis.

Procedure

The diagnosis of CHD was established using a cardiovascular ultrasound system-the GE Healthcare Vivid S6.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Hospital's Health Research Ethics Committee via letter no. FMCAB/HREC/2024/186. Informed consent was waived off as the data was collected retrospectively from the hospital medical records. All measures to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the study subjects were taken.

In this retrospective hospital-based study, I reviewed the hospital case records of all children who were referred to the Paediatric cardiology unit and had echocardiography during the period January 1, 2020 to December 31, 2024. The spectrum of various CHDs was then analysed based on the age of presentation, gender distribution, and clinical presentation. Descriptive analysis was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and presented as frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of this study. Table 1 shows the demographic representation of the patient. A total of 391 patients were seen in the Paediatric cardiology unit of which 343 (87.7%) of them had congenital heart disease. Majority, 270 (78.7%) of the

patients were one year and below at the point of diagnosis. Male patients were made up 53.9% while the females patients made up 46.1%, giving a male to female ratio of 1.1:1. Eighty four percent (84.0%) had acyanotic CHD (ACHD) while 16.0% had cyanotic CHD (CCHD).

Table1: DEMOGRAPHY

Age at diagnosis	Percentage (%)	Gender		Type of congenital heart disease	
		M	F	ACHD	CCHD
0- 24hours	0.6	1	1	2	0
>24hours – 72hours	1.5	2	3	14	1
>72hours – 1 week	5.8	8	12	18	2
>1 week – 8 weeks	28.6	54	44	87	11
>8weeks – 6months	35.0	69	51	99	21
>6months – 1year	7.3	15	10	21	4
>1year – 5years	13.4	19	27	33	13
>5years – 12years	7.0	14	10	21	3
>12years	0.9	3	0	3	0
TOTAL	100.0	185 (53.9%)	158 (46.1%)	288 (84.0%)	55 (16.0%)

ACHD: Acyanotic congenital heart diseases, CCHD: Cyanotic congenital heart disease

The patients presented with array of symptoms, some with single symptom while others had a combination of symptoms. Sixty-three percent (217) presented with referral to paediatric cardiology clinic on account of incidental finding of murmur on examination, cyanosis with murmur and failure to thrive in 36 (10.5%). Two (0.6%) patients presented as purely failure to thrive. Those that were admitted to the emergency paediatric unit presented either in congestive cardiac failure 8 (2.4%) or with severe bronchopneumonia 2 (0.6%). Two (0.6%) patients were admitted in hyper cyanotic spells. One (0.3%) patient presented to the clinic for 2nd opinion echocardiography. Twenty-nine (8.7%) were already diagnosed with CHD and transferred care for possible enrolment into open heart surgery that was going on at the facility then while there were 6 (1.8%) on follow up, post cardiac repair.

Table 2 shows the distribution of different CHDs with gender. Of the 288 patients with ACHD, ventricular septal defect (24.9%) was the commonest, followed by atrial septal defect (ASD) (13.8%) and patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) (13.1%) respectively. Several of the

patients had more than one shunt defect which included VSD + ASD in 25 patients (8.6%), VSD + PDA in 18 patients (6.2%) and ASD +PDA in 8 patients (2.7%). Atrioventricular septal defect (AVSD) was seen in 22 (7.6%) patients of which 18 (81.8) had complete AVSD.

Tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) (47.2%) was the commonest CCHD and was seen in different forms: as simple TOF in 19 patients, Pentalogy of Fallot in 4 patients, TOF canal in 2 patients and Pentalogy of Fallot with PDA in one patient. This was followed by Transposition of the great arteries (TGA) which occurred in 7 patients (12.7%) and double outlet right ventricle (DORV) which was seen in 6 patients (10.9%)

Table 2: Distribution of some CHDs with gender

ACYANOTIC CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE				CYANOTIC CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE			
TYPE	M	F	TOTAL	TYPE	M	F	TOTAL
VSD	43	29	72	TOF	5	21	26
ASD	21	19	40	TGA	2	5	7
PDA	20	18	38	DORV	5	1	6
Partial AVSD	3	1	4	Tricuspid atresia	2	2	4
Complete AVSD	12	6	18	Truncus arteriosus	1	0	1
Coarctation of the aorta	3	0	3	HLHS	0	2	2
VSD + ASD	12	13	25	VSD + Severe PS	3	0	3
VSD + PDA	8	10	18	Single Atrium	1	0	1
Malposed Great arteries with VSD and Infective endocarditis	0	1	1	Heterotaxia	1	1	2
Dextroposition with VSD and PDA	0	1	1	Criss cross heart	0	1	1

VSD: Ventricular septal defect, ASD: Atrial septal defect, PDA: Patent ductus arteriosus, AVSD: Atrioventricular septal defect, TOF: Tetralogy of Fallot, TGA: Transposition of the great arteries, DORV: Double outlet right ventricle, HLHS: Hypoplastic left heart syndrome, PS: Pulmonary stenosis

Seventy-one (20.7%) of the children were syndromic of which some were identifiable and others unidentifiable. Six of them had CCHD while the other 65 patients had ACHD. The commonly identifiable syndrome with the highest occurrence was Down syndrome which was seen in 52 (15.2%) patients. Edward syndrome was seen in 3 (0.9) and congenital rubella syndrome in 2 (0.6). Twelve (3.5%) children had dysmorphic facies which could not be classified as they were yet to perform karyotyping. Of the 71 that were syndromic, eleven of

them had VSD while 6 had PDA.

Cardiac surgery was performed on 57 (16.6%) of the subjects. The surgery included palliative surgery in 4(1.2%), PDA ligation in 7(2.0%) and open-heart surgery in 46(13.4%). 3 subjects were labelled inoperable of which 1 died while the other 2 are still being followed at the Paediatric cardiology unit. The inoperable cases have Criss cross heart with severe pulmonary arterial hypertension. The cardiac lesion types that were operated is shown in table 3

Table 3: Cardiac lesion operated on

Cardia lesions	Number operated	Open heart surgery	Palliative surgery	PDA ligation
CYANOTIC CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE				
TOF	9	9	0	NA
TGA	3	1	2	NA
DORV	2	2	0	NA
VSD + Severe PS	1	1	0	NA
Tricuspid atresia	1	0	1	NA
ACYANOTIC CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE				
VSD	12	11	1	0
PDA	7	0	0	7
VSD + PDA	5	5	0	0
ASD	4	4	0	0
COMPLETE AVSD	3	3	0	0
VSD + ASD	3	3	0	0
VSD + PS	3	3	0	0
VALVULAR PS	2	2	0	0
ASD + PS	1	1	0	0
PARTIAL AVSD	1	1	0	0

TOF: Tetralogy of Fallot, TGA Transposition of Great Arteries; DORV: Double outlet right ventricles, VSD: Ventricular septal defect, PS: Pulmonary stenosis, PDA: Patent ductus arteriosus ASD: Atrial Septal Defect, AVSD: Atrioventricular septal defect. NA: Not applicable

The mortality rate was 5.8% (20). Sixty five percent (13) of them died from complication of the primary condition while 7 (25%) had open heart surgery and died from the complications of the surgery.

List of congenital heart disease by mortality

TYPES	Number	Percentage	Died from primary disease	Post-surgery
Tetralogy of Fallot	4	27.3%	0	4
Complete atrioventricular septal defect	5	22.7%	4	1
Ventricular septal defect	4	18.2%	4	0
Atrial septal defect	2	9.1%	0	2
Truncus Arteriosus	2	9.1%	2	0
Transposition of the great arteries	1	4.5%	1	0
Patent ductus arteriosus	1	4.5%	1	0
Congenital mitral stenosis + ventricular septal defect	1	4.5%	1	0

Sixty-three (18.4%) patients were lost to follow up of which 60 (95.2%) of them had CHD while 3 (4.8%) had cyanotic CHD.

DISCUSSION

This study outlines the clinical spectrum, gender distribution, and age at diagnosis for children presenting with congenital heart disease (CHD) in Federal Medical Centre, Abuja North Central, Nigeria. The study found a significant leaning toward acyanotic cases maintaining a ratio of 5.2:1. Eighty four percent (288) of the patient had acyanotic CHD (ACHD) while 16.0% (55) had cyanotic CHD (CCHD). These findings align with broader literature^{10,11} but showed a higher acyanotic prevalence than studies by Masood et al²⁰ of 58% and Meshran of et al²¹ of 11%.

The study noted no significant gender disparity with M:F ratio of 1.1:1 which aligns with findings by Khan et al²² and Otaigbe et al.¹³ However Masood et al²⁰ noted significant gender disparity. The high prevalence of male in their study might be potentially due to socio-cultural health seeking behaviour favouring male children. While the overall ratio was balanced, specific defect showed gender leanings. Gender difference was seen with specific heart disease like VSD and AVSD which were commoner in male while TOF was commonest in female. A study by Khaleed at al²³ showed AVSD commoner in female.

Early diagnosis is a trend in this facility, though it lags slightly behind international benchmark for neonatal detection. Majority, 280 (78.8%) of the subject were diagnosed before their first birthday in consonance with Wannu et al²⁴ and Massod et al²⁰ but higher than the 42.5% recorded by Sadoh et al²⁵ in a multicentre study. Most diagnoses were made between 8 weeks to 6 months of age. Only 7.6% were diagnosed within the first month of life which is significantly lower than the 17% and 29.2% reported in Sadoh et al and Massod et al respectively.^{20,25} This could be due to the fact that our facility is yet to commence new born screening of neonates for CHD accounting for the later presentation.

The study attributes the trend of early diagnosis to increasing awareness with the most common reason for referral being incidental discovery of a heart murmur during routine examinations. The study notes a high prevalence of symptomatic cases compared to another Nigerian research. Sixty-three (63.3%) of these children presented with associated signs such as dysmorphic facies, cyanosis and failure to thrive. This is significantly higher than the 36% documented by Wannu et al.²⁴ While Abah et al²⁶ reported respiratory distress (74%) as the top symptom, the study highlights a broader spectrum of physical signs.

The study identifies Ventricular septal defect (VSD) as the most prevalent condition, consistent with many global and local Nigerian studies though the specific rate varies by region.⁹⁻¹⁵ The prevalence rate of 24.9% for VSD in our study is lower than 55.3% and 34.9% reported by Ibadin et al²⁷ and Abah et al²⁶ respectively but higher than 11% reported by Parker et al.²⁸ Atrial septal defect (ASD) is the second and patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) the third most common CHD seen in our study. Mansour et al²⁹ reported PDA with the highest prevalence. This is not surprising as the study involved only neonates who were delivered in the hospital and had echocardiogram performed within 24 hours when the ductus is yet to close. Tetralogy of Fallot was the commonest cyanotic CHD seen at 34.5%. This pattern is also similar to other studies in Nigeria and other parts of the world.¹⁰⁻¹⁷

A significant portion of the CHD population presented with identifiable genetic syndrome with Trisomy 21 (Down syndrome) being the most prominent. Down syndrome was seen in 52 (15.2%) patients. Edward syndrome was seen in 3 (0.9%) and congenital rubella syndrome in 2 (0.6%). Noonan's syndrome and Marfan's syndrome was seen in 1 (0.3%) patient each. Twelve (3.5%) children had dysmorphic facies which could not be classified as they were yet to perform karyotyping. Among the 71 syndromic patients, VSD was the commonest defect (11 patients) followed by PDA (6 patients). Amenawon et al³⁰ reported the highest prevalence of atrioventricular septal defect in children with Down syndrome. Diagnosis of Down syndrome was made based on both physical features and confirmed in some with genetic testing.

This study highlights a pivotal shift in local capacity, marking the commencement of open-heart surgery at the centre in 2023. The facility has since then been receiving referral for open heart surgery with some being performed in our centre and others in other centres. Most of the surgeries relied on non-governmental organization (NGO) sponsorship or corporate social responsibility (CSR). Government funding was minimal and "out-of-pocket" payments were generally limited to less complex procedures like

PDA ligation. Few were funded by federal and state government. Those funded out of pocket were PDA ligation. This goes to show how expensive cardiac surgeries are. There is a documented increase in surgical access of 16.6% compared to previous Nigerian studies that reported 7.2%.¹³ The surgeries performed in this facility included palliative surgery in 4(1.2%), PDA ligation in 7(2.0%) and open-heart surgery in 46(13.4%). Three subjects were labelled inoperable of which 1 died while the other 2 are still being followed at the Paediatric cardiology unit.

The study reported a mortality rate of 6.4% (22 patients), which is notably lower than figures from Abah et al²⁶ in Makurdi and Sadoh et al²⁵ in Benin who reported 12.8% and 18.8% respectively. Fourteen patients (63.6%) died from complication of the primary condition while 8 (36.4%) had open heart surgery and died from the complications of the surgery. Post operative complications occurred mostly in children that had tetralogy of Fallot.

A significant hurdle in the centre is the high rate of patients (18.4%) who stopped seeking care at our facility and were lost to follow up. The attrition rate was more in children with ACHD (95.2%). This trend is similar to other studies in Nigeria as most parents are often overwhelmed by the cost implication in managing such children hence, they resign to their fate hence seeking alternative or traditional ways.^{13,25,26}

This study is the first in exploring the prevalence and pattern of CHD among children in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

The limitation of this study is that this was a single hospital-based study. A large multicentre study will be good in identifying the accurate prevalence and pattern of CHD among the children in our state, region and country

CONCLUSION

The pattern of various CHDs in our study is largely similar to pre-existing literature. The high mortality might be attributed to non-availability of surgical intervention. The establishment of cardiothoracic centre with the support of government and non-

government agencies (NGO) may help in the outcome.

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Ethical approval: The study was approved by the facility's Health and Research Ethics Committee

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